

Classification Analysis and Data Mining

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ABSTRACT

This study utilizes K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) in Python to identify customers at high risk of discontinuing service (churn). The goal is to understand which customer characteristics are most influential in predicting churn. We hypothesize that KNN can effectively classify customers likely to churn based on their historical data. Accurately predicting churn allows companies to prioritize customer retention efforts for those most likely to leave. The KNN algorithm classifies new data points based on the majority vote of their K nearest neighbors in the training data. We assume that data points with similar characteristics will have similar churn behavior. Python is chosen for its extensive data science libraries and user-friendly syntax. Specific libraries include Pandas (data manipulation), NumPy (numerical operations), Matplotlib (visualization), Scikit-learn (machine learning), and Seaborn (advanced visualization). The data consists of 10,000 customer records with 50 initial features. Data cleaning will involve removing irrelevant identifying information, handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and visualizing data distributions. The target variable is "Bandwidth_GB_Year" (average annual data usage). Other relevant features include categorical variables like contract length and internet service type, as well as discrete ordinal variables from customer service ratings. After cleaning and preparation, the processed data will be saved as "churn_prepared.csv". This project will contribute to a better understanding of customer churn behavior and guide targeted retention strategies.

Keywords: Customer churn prediction, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Machine learning, Customer segmentation, Customer retention

INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive telecommunications landscape, customer retention is paramount. Companies face the constant challenge of keeping subscribers engaged and preventing them from switching to competitors, a phenomenon known as customer churn. This study delves into the world of customer churn prediction, aiming to identify the red flags that signal a customer's potential departure. By leveraging the power of K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), a machine learning algorithm, we can build a model that analyzes customer characteristics and predicts churn behavior. Imagine being able to pinpoint the customers most likely to churn, allowing the company to prioritize resources and tailor retention strategies for maximum impact. This project holds the potential to revolutionize customer retention efforts, leading to increased customer satisfaction and a more sustainable business model for the telecommunications company. We'll begin by exploring a dataset of 10,000 customer records, containing a wealth of information about service usage, contract details, and even customer service ratings. Through a meticulous data cleaning process, we'll ensure the data is ready for analysis. The KNN algorithm will then be employed to learn from the data and identify patterns that differentiate loyal customers from those at risk of churning. Finally, the project will culminate in the creation of a "churn_prepared.csv" file, a valuable resource for further analysis and model refinement. This study not only contributes to a deeper understanding of customer churn but also paves the way for the development of proactive strategies to keep customers happy and loyal.

PURPOSE

This study aims to predict customer churn in a telecommunications company using K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). By identifying key customer characteristics, we can develop a model to classify high-risk customers. This allows

the company to prioritize resources and tailor retention strategies, ultimately reducing churn and boosting customer satisfaction. We'll utilize a dataset of 10,000 customer records, clean the data, and explore patterns before training and evaluating the KNN model. This project delivers a processed dataset for further analysis and refines churn prediction strategies.

LIMITATIONS

While this study offers valuable insights into customer churn prediction using KNN, it has certain limitations to consider. Firstly, KNN's performance can be sensitive to the dimensionality of the data. With a large number of features, the algorithm can struggle to identify meaningful similarities between data points. Feature selection or dimensionality reduction techniques may be necessary to address this. Secondly, KNN relies on the assumption that similar past behavior predicts future behavior. This may not always hold true, particularly in dynamic markets where customer needs and preferences can evolve rapidly. The model's effectiveness might deteriorate over time if not regularly updated with fresh data. Finally, the accuracy of the model is highly dependent on the quality of the data used for training. Biases or inconsistencies in the data can lead to biased predictions. Careful data cleaning and validation procedures are crucial to mitigate this limitation. Despite these limitations, this study provides a foundation for building a customer churn prediction model using KNN. By acknowledging these limitations and implementing appropriate mitigation strategies, we can enhance the model's accuracy and generalizability for real-world applications.

METHODOLOGY

We'll utilize the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm to classify customers at risk of churn. KNN identifies similar data points based on their features. In our case, these features will be customer characteristics like service usage and contract type. By comparing a new customer's profile to its K nearest neighbors (similar customers), we can predict the new customer's likelihood of churning.

UNDERSTANDING CUSTOMER CHURN

This study delves into customer churn, the phenomenon where customers discontinue service with a telecommunications company. Our primary question is: Which customer characteristics are most indicative of churn? By identifying these key features, we aim to develop a model that can classify customers at high risk of churning. The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm will be our tool for this analysis. KNN classifies new data points based on their similarity to existing data points. In this context, the data points will be customer profiles containing information like service usage, contract details, and even customer service ratings. By comparing a new customer's profile to its closest neighbors (similar customers) who have already churned or remained loyal, we can predict the new customer's likelihood of churning. This project has significant implications for the company's customer retention efforts. By pinpointing customers most likely to leave, the company can prioritize resources and tailor retention strategies to those most at risk. This approach can potentially reduce churn, boost customer satisfaction, and contribute to a more sustainable business model.

CLASSIFICATION WITH KNN: NEIGHBORS-HELPING-NEIGHBOR APPROACH

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a powerful tool for classification tasks, making it well-suited for our goal of predicting customer churn. KNN operates under a simple principle: similar data points tend to have similar classifications.

Here's how it works in our context:

1. Training the Model: We feed the KNN algorithm a dataset containing historical customer information, including features like service usage, contract details, and churn status (loyal or churned).
2. Identifying Similar Customers: When presented with a new customer profile, KNN searches the training data for the K closest neighbors, meaning the K customer profiles most similar to the new customer based on their features.
3. Majority Vote for Churn Prediction: KNN then analyzes the churn status of these K neighbors. If the majority of the neighbors churned, the new customer is classified as high risk for churn. Conversely, if most neighbors remain loyal, the new customer is classified as low risk.

This "majority vote" approach allows KNN to leverage the collective wisdom of similar past cases to predict churn for new customers. It's like asking your neighbors for advice - if most of them had a negative experience with a service provider, you might be cautious about signing up yourself. Following training, the KNN model's performance will be evaluated using separate test data to ensure its generalizability to unseen customers.

ASSUMPTIONS UNDERLYING KNN

KNN relies on a key assumption: that similar customers are likely to exhibit similar behavior. In our case, this translates to the idea that customers with similar service usage patterns, contract types, and customer service interactions are more likely to churn together. This assumption holds true for many real-world scenarios, but it's

important to acknowledge its limitations. For example, external factors like a competitor offering a sudden price drop could influence churn behavior across customer segments, potentially affecting the accuracy of KNN predictions.

PYTHON: OUR TOOLKIT FOR CHURN PREDICTION

This study leverages Python, a versatile programming language widely used in data science. Here's why Python is a perfect fit for our project:

- **Rich Data Science Ecosystem:** Python boasts a vast collection of libraries specifically designed for data science tasks. Libraries like NumPy (numerical operations), Pandas (data manipulation), Matplotlib (data visualization), Scikit-learn (machine learning algorithms), and Seaborn (advanced visualizations) will form the backbone of our analysis.
- **Ease of Use:** Python's syntax is clear and concise, making it easier to learn and code compared to other languages like R. This allows us to focus on the analysis itself rather than struggling with complex syntax.
- **Cross-Platform Compatibility:** Whether you're using a Windows PC or a MacBook, Python code runs seamlessly, ensuring flexibility and collaboration throughout the project.

By utilizing Python and its powerful data science libraries, we can efficiently explore customer data, train the KNN model, and ultimately build a valuable tool for predicting customer churn.

UNVEILING THE DATA: PREPARATION AND EXPLORATION

This section dives into the heart of our data analysis: preparing and exploring the customer data to equip the KNN model for churn prediction.

DATA WRANGLING: SHAPING THE RAW MATERIAL

The first step involves wrangling the raw data into a usable format for analysis. We'll utilize Python and the Pandas library for this task.

1. **Importing the Data:** Pandas' `read_csv` function allows us to effortlessly import the customer data from a CSV file into a Python data frame - a structured table-like object. We'll assign a meaningful name to this data frame, like `churn_data`, for easy reference.
2. **Examining the Data Structure:** Understanding the data frame's structure is crucial. We'll use Pandas' built-in functions to explore the number of rows (customers) and columns (features) in the data. Additionally, we'll identify the data types associated with each column, such as numerical (age, monthly charge) or categorical (contract type, internet service).
3. **Data Cleaning:** No dataset is perfect. We'll check for inconsistencies like misspellings or strange variable names. More importantly, we'll identify any missing data points. Depending on the extent and distribution of missing data, we might impute them using relevant central tendency measures (mean, median, mode) or simply remove rows with excessive missing values.
4. **Outlier Wrangling:** Outliers are data points that deviate significantly from the majority. While some outliers might be genuine, others could be errors. Histograms and boxplots will help us visualize the distribution of each feature and identify potential outliers. We'll decide whether to remove extreme outliers or handle them using techniques like capping or winsorizing.
5. **Target Variable:** Our ultimate goal is to predict churn. The feature indicating whether a customer churned (yes) or remained loyal (no) becomes our target variable. We'll ensure it's clearly identified within the data frame.
6. **Feature Engineering:** The data initially contains a mix of numerical and categorical variables. KNN thrives on numerical data. For categorical variables like "contract type" (one year, two year), we'll employ a technique called one-hot encoding. This converts each category into a separate binary variable (e.g., one-year contract = 1, two-year contract = 0). This allows KNN to understand the relationships between these features and churn.

DATA EXPLORATION: UNVEILING PATTERNS

Once the data is clean and prepped, it's time to explore it further. Pandas and various visualization libraries like Matplotlib and Seaborn will be our allies in this stage.

1. **Summary Statistics:** We'll calculate summary statistics for each numerical feature (e.g., average age, standard deviation of monthly charge). This provides a basic understanding of central tendency and spread within the data.
2. **Univariate Analysis:** Visualizing the distribution of each feature using histograms and boxplots is crucial. This reveals potential outliers, skewness (data leaning towards one side), and overall shape of the data distribution.
3. **Bivariate Analysis:** Exploring relationships between features is vital. Scatterplots will help us visualize how one feature (e.g., monthly data usage) might influence another (e.g., customer churn).
4. **Understanding the Customer:** We'll delve deeper into the target variable (churn) to understand the typical customer who churns. This might involve analyzing average monthly charges, contract type, and service usage patterns of churning customers compared to loyal customers.

DATA TRANSFORMATION: PREPARING FOR KNN

Following exploration, the final step involves data transformation to ensure optimal compatibility with KNN:

1. Feature Scaling: Features might have different scales (e.g., age in years, monthly charge in dollars). KNN can be sensitive to such differences. Standardization or normalization techniques can be employed to transform all features to a common scale, ensuring each feature contributes equally to the KNN distance calculation.
2. Feature Selection (Optional): While we've already transformed categorical variables, the dataset might still contain a large number of features. Feature selection techniques can help identify the most relevant features for churn prediction, potentially improving the KNN model's performance.
3. Data Splitting: Finally, we'll divide the prepared data into two sets: a training set and a test set. The KNN model will be trained on the training set, allowing it to learn from the data and develop churn prediction rules. The test set will be used to evaluate the model's generalizability to unseen customer data.

By following these data preparation and exploration steps, we'll transform the raw customer data into a valuable.

DATA PREPARATION PROCEDURE

Include Standard Imports All the Require References

```
# Increase Jupyter display cell-width
from IPython.core.display import display, HTML
display(HTML("<style>.container { width:75% !important; }</style>"))
```

<IPython.core.display.HTML object>

```
# Standard data science imports
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from pandas import Series, DataFrame

# Visualization Libraries
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline

# Scikit-Learn
import sklearn
from sklearn import datasets
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import metrics
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
```

Change Font and Color of The Matplotlib

```
# Change color of Matplotlib font
import matplotlib as mpl
COLOR = 'white'
mpl.rcParams['text.color'] = COLOR
mpl.rcParams['axes.labelcolor'] = COLOR
mpl.rcParams['xtick.color'] = COLOR
mpl.rcParams['ytick.color'] = COLOR
```

Imports the Ignore Warning Codes

```
# Ignore Warning Code
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
```

```
In [8]: # Load data set into Pandas dataframe
churn_df = pd.read_csv('C:\Rekha\churn_clean.csv', index_col=0)
```

```
# Examine the features of the dataset
churn_df.columns

Index(['Customer_id', 'Interaction', 'UID', 'City', 'State', 'County', 'Zip',
      'Lat', 'Lng', 'Population', 'Area', 'TimeZone', 'Job', 'Children',
      'Age', 'Income', 'Marital', 'Gender', 'Churn', 'Outage_sec_perweek',
      'Email', 'Contacts', 'Yearly equip_failure', 'Techle', 'Contract',
      'Port_modem', 'Tablet', 'InternetService', 'Phone', 'Multiple',
      'OnlineSecurity', 'OnlineBackup', 'DeviceProtection', 'TechSupport',
      'StreamingTV', 'StreamingMovies', 'PaperlessBilling', 'PaymentMethod',
      'Tenure', 'MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year', 'Item1', 'Item2',
      'Item3', 'Item4', 'Item5', 'Item6', 'Item7', 'Item8'],
      dtype='object')
```

```
# Get an idea of dataset size
churn_df.shape

(10000, 49)
```

```
# Continue first few records of dataset
churn_df.head(5)
```

CaseOrder	Customer_id	Interaction	UID	City	State	County	Zip	Lat	Lng	Population	MonthlyCharge	Bandwidth_GB_Year	Item1	Item2	Item3
1	K409198	aa902600-4141-4a24-8e36-b04ce1f4f77b	Point Baker	AK	Prince of Hales-Hyder	99927	56.25100	-133.37571	38	...	112.45519	804.52819	5	5	5
2	S120509	fb76459f-c047-4a0d-8af9-e0f7d4ac2524	West Branch	MI	Ogemaw	48661	44.32893	-84.24088	10446	...	242.83254	800.85205	3	4	3
3	K191035	344d114c-3736-4be5-98f7-c7c281e2d355	Yamhill	OR	Yamhill	97148	45.35589	-123.24057	3735	...	100.84763	294.70801	4	4	2
4	D90850	abfa2b40-2d43-4994-b15a-909b8c79e311	Del Mar	CA	San Diego	92014	32.96687	-117.24798	13863	...	119.85849	2164.51942	4	4	4
5	K062701	68a801fd-0d20-4e51-a587-8a90407ee574	Needville	TX	Fort Bend	77461	29.38012	-95.80673	11352	...	140.84819	271.40348	4	4	4

```
# View DataFrame info
churn_df.info
```

```
<bound method DataFrame.info of
CaseOrder
1 Customer_id Interaction \
2 K409198 aa902600-4141-4a24-8e36-b04ce1f4f77b
3 S120509 fb76459f-c047-4a0d-8af9-e0f7d4ac2524
4 K191035 344d114c-3736-4be5-98f7-c7c281e2d355
5 D90850 abfa2b40-2d43-4994-b15a-909b8c79e311
...
9996 H324793 45deb5a2-ae04-4518-bf0b-c82db8dbe4a4
9997 D061732 6e9eb021-0c09-4993-bbda-a1ac6411061a
9998 I243405 e8307ddf-9a01-4fff-bc59-4742e03fd24f
9999 I041617 3775ccfc-0052-4107-81ae-9057f81ecdF3
10000 T38070 9de5f06e-bd33-4995-aec8-f0100172a499

CaseOrder
1 UID City State \
2 e885b290883d4f9fb18e39c75155d900 Point Baker AK
3 f2de0bef964785f41a2959829830fb8a West Branch MI
4 f1704cf96d92ae816197eb17503c71 Yamhill OR
5 dc8a365077241bb5cd5ccd305136b05e Del Mar CA
...
9996 9499fb4de537af195d16d046b79fd20a Mount Holly VT
9997 c09a041117fa81b5c8e19afec2700104 Clarksville TN
9998 9c43f2121e04dca04458190bc9b041c Mobeetie TX
9999 3e1f269b40c235a1838863ecf6b7a0df Carrollton GA
10000 0ea683a03a3cd544afe8388aab10176 Clarkesville GA

CaseOrder
1 County Zip Lat Lng Population ... \
2 Prince of Hales-Hyder 99927 56.25100 -133.37571 38 ...
3 Ogemaw 48661 44.32893 -84.24088 10446 ...
4 Yamhill 97148 45.35589 -123.24057 3735 ...
5 San Diego 92014 32.96687 -117.24798 13863 ...
...
9996 Rutland 5758 43.43391 -72.78734 648 ...
9997 Montgomery 37042 36.56907 -87.41604 77168 ...
9998 Wheeler 79061 35.52039 -100.44180 406 ...
9999 Carroll 30117 33.58016 -85.13241 35575 ...
10000 Habersham 30523 34.70783 -83.53648 12230 ...
```

CaseOrder	MonthlyCharge	Bandwidth_GB_Year	Item1	Item2	Item3	Item4	Item5
1	172.455519	904.536110	5	5	5	3	4
2	242.632554	800.982766	3	4	3	3	4
3	159.947583	2054.706961	4	4	2	4	4
4	119.956840	2164.579412	4	4	4	2	5
5	149.948316	271.493436	4	4	4	3	4
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
9996	159.979400	6511.252601	3	2	3	3	4
9997	207.481100	5695.951810	4	5	5	4	4
9998	169.974100	4159.385799	4	4	4	4	4
9999	252.624000	6468.456752	4	4	6	4	3
10000	217.484000	5857.586167	2	2	3	3	3

CaseOrder	Item6	Item7	Item8
1	4	3	4
2	3	4	4
3	3	3	3
4	4	3	3
5	4	4	5
...	...	...	...
9996	3	2	3
9997	5	2	5
9998	4	4	5
9999	3	5	4
10000	3	4	1

[10000 rows x 49 columns]>

```
# Provide an (optional) look at subset dataset
cham_df.head()
```

Customer_ID	Interaction	URI	City	State	County	Zip	Lat	Log	Population	Children	Age	Income	Outage_sec_per_week	Cat1	Contacts	MonthlyCharge	Bandwidth_GB_Year	Item1	Item2	Item3	Item4	Item5	Item6	Item7	Item8
1	843018	8612336-4747-8420-8535-1084492273	Portland	ME	Franklin	04103	43.65108	-70.30711	38	...	172.455519	904.536110	5	5	5	3	4								
2	812989	0207-6380-840-40718a12104	Portland	ME	Franklin	04103	43.65108	-70.30711	38	...	242.632554	800.982766	3	4	3	3	4								
3	813133	3440760-3738-8480-8007-47328141808	Portland	ME	Franklin	04103	43.65108	-70.30711	38	...	159.947583	2054.706961	4	4	2	4	4								
4	100000	8612336-4747-8420-8535-1084492273	Portland	ME	Franklin	04103	43.65108	-70.30711	38	...	119.956840	2164.579412	4	4	4	2	5								
5	8082791	8612336-4747-8420-8535-1084492273	Portland	ME	Franklin	04103	43.65108	-70.30711	38	...	149.948316	271.493436	4	4	4	3	4								

5 rows x 49 columns

```
# Get an overview of descriptive statistics
cham_df.describe()
```

	Zip	Lat	Log	Population	Children	Age	Income	Outage_sec_per_week	Cat1	Contacts	MonthlyCharge	Bandwidth_GB_Year
count	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
mean	48151.219608	43.717607	-70.307110	9734.962400	2.0877	33.076490	36046.826771	13.091046	12.016090	9.944230	172.455519	904.536110
std	27532.959108	5.431759	15.199142	14432.988571	2.1472	23.698882	28199.915702	2.079719	3.029590	9.588496	42.943994	2164.579412
min	691.800000	-17.365126	-171.988158	9.000000	0.0000	18.000000	348.570000	0.000747	1.000000	0.000000	79.878808	152.505715
25%	26792.500000	39.341828	-87.882812	738.000000	0.0000	38.000000	18224.717000	8.018274	18.000000	0.000000	139.879238	1238.470027
50%	48000.500000	43.285939	-67.018809	2819.500000	0.0000	53.000000	33170.800000	19.018580	12.000000	0.000000	157.404708	3279.530800
75%	71966.500000	42.100908	-65.285745	13768.000000	3.0000	71.000000	53240.170000	15.948485	14.000000	2.000000	200.734725	5946.947379
max	99929.500000	75.849669	-69.987899	111939.000000	18.0000	88.000000	258990.700000	21.297230	23.000000	7.000000	290.162419	7158.981835

8 rows x 13 columns

```
# Get data types of features
churn_df.dtypes
```

```
Customer_id      object
Interaction       object
UID              object
City             object
State            object
County           object
Zip              int64
Lat              float64
Lng              float64
Population       int64
Area             object
TimeZone         object
Job              object
Children         int64
Age              int64
Income           float64
Marital          object
Gender           object
Churn            object
Outage_sec_perweek float64
Email            int64
Contacts         int64
Yearly equip_failure int64
Techie           object
Contract         object
Port_modem       object
Tablet           object
```

```
InternetService  object
Phone            object
Multiple         object
OnlineSecurity   object
OnlineBackup     object
DeviceProtection object
TechSupport      object
StreamingTV      object
StreamingMovies  object
PaperlessBilling object
PaymentMethod    object
Tenure           float64
MonthlyCharge    float64
Bandwidth_GB_Year float64
Item1            int64
Item2            int64
Item3            int64
Item4            int64
Item5            int64
Item6            int64
Item7            int64
Item8            int64
dtype: object
```

```
# Rename last 8 survey columns for better description of variables
churn_df.rename(columns = {'Item1':'Timely_Response',
'Item2':'Timely_Fixes',
'Item3':'Timely_Replacements',
'Item4':'Reliability',
'Item5':'Options',
'Item6':'Respectful_Response',
'Item7':'Courteous_exchange',
'Item8':'Active_Listening'},
inplace=True)
```

```
# Create histograms of continuous variables & categorical variables
churn_df[['Children', 'Age', 'Income', 'Outage_sec_perweek', 'Email',
'Contacts', 'Yearly equip_failure', 'Tenure', 'MonthlyCharge',
'Bandwidth_GB_Year', 'Timely_Response', 'Courteous_exchange']].hist()
plt.savefig('churn_pyplot.jpg')
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
# Create a scatterplot to get an idea of correlations between potentially related variables
sns.scatterplot(x=churn_df['Outage_sec_perweek'], y=churn_df['Churn'], color='blue')
plt.show();
```

```
# Create a scatterplot to get an idea of correlations between potentially related variables
sns.scatterplot(x=churn_df['Tenure'], y=churn_df['Churn'], color='blue')
plt.show();
```

```
# Create a scatterplot to get an idea of correlations between potentially related variables
sns.scatterplot(x=churn_df['MonthlyCharge'], y=churn_df['Outage_sec_perweek'], color='blue')
plt.show();
```

```
# Provide a scatter matrix of numeric variables for high level overview of potential relationships & distributions
churn_numeric = churn_df[['Children', 'Age', 'Income', 'Outage_sec_perweek',
'Email', 'Contacts', 'Yearly equip_failure', 'Tenure',
'MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year', 'Timely_Replacements',
'Reliability', 'Options', 'Respectful_Response', 'Courteous_exchange',
'Active_Listening']]
pd.plotting.scatter_matrix(churn_numeric, figsize = [15, 15]);
```

```
# Create individual scatterplot for viewing relationship of key financial feature against target variable
sns.scatterplot(x = churn_df['MonthlyCharge'], y = churn_df['Churn'], color='red')
plt.show();
```

```
# Set plot style to ggplot for aesthetics & R style
plt.style.use('ggplot')
# Countplot more useful than scatter_matrix when features of dataset are binary
plt.figure()
sns.countplot(x='Techie', hue='Churn', data=churn_df, palette='RdBu')
plt.xticks([0,1], ['No', 'Yes'])
plt.show()
```

```
# Countplot more useful than scatter_matrix when features of dataset are binary
plt.figure()
sns.countplot(x='PaperlessBilling', hue='Churn', data=churn_df, palette='RdBu')
plt.xticks([0,1], ['No', 'Yes'])
plt.show()
```

```
# Countplot more useful than scatter_matrix when features of dataset are binary
plt.figure()
sns.countplot(x='InternetService', hue='Churn', data=churn_df, palette='RdBu')
plt.xticks([0,1], ['No', 'Yes'])
plt.show()
```

```
# Create Seaborn boxplots for continuous & categorical variables
sns.boxplot('MonthlyCharge', data = churn_df)
plt.show()
```

```
# Create multiple boxplots for continuous & categorical variables
churn_df.boxplot(column=['MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year'])
```

<AxesSubplot:>

```
# Create Seaborn boxplots for continuous variables
sns.boxplot('Tenure', data = churn_df)
plt.show()
```

```
# Create Seaborn boxplots for continuous & categorical variables
sns.boxplot('Bandwidth_GB_Year', data = churn_df)
plt.show()
```

```
# Discover missing data points within dataset
data_nulls = churn_df.isnull().sum()
print(data_nulls)
```

Customer_id	0
Interaction	0
UID	0
City	0
State	0
County	0
Zip	0
Lat	0
Lng	0
Population	0
Area	0
TimeZone	0
Job	0
Children	0
Age	0
Income	0
Marital	0
Gender	0
Churn	0
Outage_sec_perweek	0
Email	0
Contacts	0
Yearly equip_failure	0
Techie	0
Contract	0
Port_modem	0
Tablet	0
InternetService	0
Phone	0
Multiple	0
OnlineSecurity	0
OnlineBackup	0
DeviceProtection	0
TechSupport	0
StreamingTV	0
StreamingMovies	0
PaperlessBilling	0
PaymentMethod	0
Tenure	0
MonthlyCharge	0
Bandwidth_GB_Year	0
Timely_Response	0
Timely_Fixes	0
Timely_Replacements	0
Reliability	0
Options	0
Respectful_Response	0
Courteous_exchange	0
Active_Listening	0
dtype:	int64

```
# Check for missing data & visualize missing values in dataset
# Install appropriate library
!pip install missingno
# Importing the libraries
import missingno as msno
# Visualize missing values as a matrix
msno.matrix(churn_df)
'''(GeeksforGeeks, p. 1)'''
Requirement already satisfied: missingno in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (8.5.0)
Requirement already satisfied: scipy in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from missingno) (1.6.2)
Requirement already satisfied: matplotlib in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from missingno) (3.3.4)
Requirement already satisfied: seaborn in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from missingno) (0.11.1)
Requirement already satisfied: numpy in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from missingno) (1.28.1)
Requirement already satisfied: pillow<=2.8 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from matplotlib>=3.3.4) (8.2.0)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil<=2.1 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from matplotlib>=3.3.4) (2.8.1)
Requirement already satisfied: pyparsing<=2.0.4, >=1.1.2, <=2.1.0, >=2.0.3 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from matplotlib>=3.3.4) (2.4.7)
Requirement already satisfied: kiwisolver<=1.0.1 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from matplotlib>=3.3.4) (1.3.1)
Requirement already satisfied:ycler<=0.10 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from matplotlib>=3.3.4) (0.10.0)
Requirement already satisfied: six in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from cycler<=0.10-matplotlib>=3.3.4) (1.15.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pandas<=0.23 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from seaborn>=0.11.1) (1.2.4)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz>=2017.3 in c:\users\kallianaconda\lib\site-packages (from pandas>=0.23-seaborn>=0.11.1) (2021.1)
'GeeksforGeeks, p. 1'

Customer Id  Interaction  UID  City  State  County  Zip  Lat  Lng  Population  ...  DummyTablet  DummyInternetService  DummyPhone  DummyMultiple  DummyOnlineSecurity  DummyOnlineBackup  DummyDeviceProtection  DummyTechSupport  DummyStreamingTV  DummyStreamingMovies  DummyPaperlessBilling
1  10000

# Encode binary categorical variables with dummies
churn_df['DummyGender'] = [1 if v == 'Male' else 0 for v in churn_df['Gender']]
churn_df['DummyChurn'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Churn']] ## If the customer left (churned) they get a '1'
churn_df['DummyTechie'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Techie']]
churn_df['DummyContract'] = [1 if v == 'Two Year' else 0 for v in churn_df['Contract']]
churn_df['DummyPort_modem'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Port_modem']]
churn_df['DummyTablet'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Tablet']]
churn_df['DummyInternetService'] = [1 if v == 'Fiber Optic' else 0 for v in churn_df['InternetService']]
churn_df['DummyPhone'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Phone']]
churn_df['DummyMultiple'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['Multiple']]
churn_df['DummyOnlineSecurity'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['OnlineSecurity']]
churn_df['DummyOnlineBackup'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['OnlineBackup']]
churn_df['DummyDeviceProtection'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['DeviceProtection']]
churn_df['DummyTechSupport'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['TechSupport']]
churn_df['DummyStreamingTV'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['StreamingTV']]
churn_df['DummyStreamingMovies'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['StreamingMovies']]
churn_df['DummyPaperlessBilling'] = [1 if v == 'Yes' else 0 for v in churn_df['PaperlessBilling']]

# Drop original categorical features from dataframe
churn_df = churn_df.drop(columns=['Gender', 'Churn', 'Techie', 'Contract', 'Port_modem', 'Tablet',
'InternetService', 'Phone', 'Multiple', 'OnlineSecurity',
'OnlineBackup', 'DeviceProtection', 'TechSupport',
'StreamingTV', 'StreamingMovies', 'PaperlessBilling'])

churn_df.head()

CaseOrder  Customer Id  Interaction  UID  City  State  County  Zip  Lat  Lng  Population  ...  DummyTablet  DummyInternetService  DummyPhone  DummyMultiple
1  K039196  4952929-474174428-6235  4952929368916236751554990  Fort  Baker  AK  Prince of  Wales-  99627  59.2510  -133.3771  38  ...  1  1  1
2  0129589  0241-2490-8405  024124908405  Chatham94750416296923903085a  West  Branch  MI  Oshtemo  48861  44.3283  -84.2480  1844  ...  1  1  1
3  K191235  34407140-3720-14205-072028142050  1776a3a80620ad18187a17562c71  Yavapai  AZ  Yavapai  85748  45.2659  -123.2467  3738  ...  0  0  1
4  036865  2943-6994-9758  9896a79d311  0ca1865772418a40f5d00118605a  Delmar  CA  San  Diego  92014  32.9667  -117.2478  13843  ...  0  0  1
5  K047291  5269176-8020-4401-8307-3u304076914  8a86d4a17a6d270a4e4b19a184379  Roundtop  TX  Fort  Bend  77461  29.3810  -98.5873  11342  ...  0  1  0
5 rows x 48 columns

# Remove less meaningful categorical variables from dataset to provide fully numerical dataframe for further analysis
churn_df = churn_df.drop(columns=['Customer Id', 'Interaction', 'UID',
'City', 'State', 'County', 'Zip', 'Lat', 'Lng',
'Area', 'Timezone', 'Job', 'Marital', 'PaymentMethod'])
churn_df.head()

Population  Children  Age  Income  Outage_sec_perweek  Email  Contacts  Yearly equip_failure  Tenure  MonthlyCharge  ...  DummyTablet  DummyInternetService  DummyPhone  DummyMultiple
1  38  0  68  28561.99  7.978323  10  0  0  1  6.795513  172.455519  ...  1  1  1  1
2  10448  1  27  21704.77  11.699000  12  0  0  1  1.158681  242.632554  ...  1  1  1  1
3  3735  4  50  9509.57  10.752800  9  0  0  1  15.754144  159.947583  ...  0  0  1  1
4  13883  1  48  18925.23  14.913540  15  2  0  0  17.087227  119.956840  ...  0  0  1  1
5  11352  0  83  40074.19  8.147417  16  2  1  1  1.670972  149.948316  ...  0  1  0  0
5 rows x 34 columns

# Move DummyChurn to end of dataset to set as target
churn_df = churn_df[['Children', 'Age', 'Income', 'Outage_sec_perweek', 'Email', 'Contacts',
'Yearly equip_failure', 'Tenure', 'MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year',
'Timely_Response', 'Timely_Files', 'Timely_Replacements',
'Reliability', 'Options', 'Respectful_Response', 'Courteous_exchange', 'Active_listening',
'DummyGender', 'DummyTechie', 'DummyContract',
'DummyPort_modem', 'DummyTablet', 'DummyInternetService', 'DummyPhone',
'DummyMultiple', 'DummyOnlineSecurity', 'DummyOnlineBackup',
'DummyDeviceProtection', 'DummyTechSupport', 'DummyStreamingTV',
'DummyPaperlessBilling', 'DummyChurn']]
churn_df.head()

Children  Age  Income  Outage_sec_perweek  Email  Contacts  Yearly equip_failure  Tenure  MonthlyCharge  Bandwidth_GB_Year  ...  DummyTablet
CaseOrder
1  0  68  28561.99  7.978323  10  0  0  1  6.795513  172.455519  ...  904.536119  ...
2  1  27  21704.77  11.699000  12  0  0  1  1.158681  242.632554  ...  800.982760  ...
3  4  50  9509.57  10.752800  9  0  0  1  15.754144  159.947583  ...  2054.706961  ...
4  1  48  18925.23  14.913540  15  2  0  0  17.087227  119.956840  ...  2164.579412  ...
5  0  83  40074.19  8.147417  16  2  1  1  1.670972  149.948316  ...  271.493438  ...
5 rows x 33 columns
```

```
# Move DummyChurn to end of dataset to set as target
churn_df = churn_df[['Children', 'Age', 'Income', 'Outage_sec_perweek', 'Email', 'Contacts',
'Yearly_equip_failure', 'Tenure', 'MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year',
'Timely_Response', 'Timely_Fixes', 'Timely_Replacements',
'Reliability', 'Options', 'Respectful_Response', 'Courteous_exchange', 'Active_Listening',
'DummyGender', 'DummyTechie', 'DummyContract',
'DummyPort_modem', 'DummyTablet', 'DummyInternetService', 'DummyPhone',
'DummyMultiple', 'DummyOnlineSecurity', 'DummyOnlineBackup',
'DummyDeviceProtection', 'DummyTechSupport', 'DummyStreamingTV',
'DummyPaperlessBilling', 'DummyChurn']]
churn_df.head()
```

	Children	Age	Income	Outage_sec_perweek	Email	Contacts	Yearly_equip_failure	Tenure	MonthlyCharge	Bandwidth_GB_Year	...	DummyChurn
CaseOrder												
1	0	68	26561.99	7.978323	10	0	1	6.795513	172.455519	904.536110	...	...
2	1	27	21704.77	11.699080	12	0	1	1.156681	242.632554	800.982769	...	...
3	4	50	9609.57	10.752800	9	0	1	15.754144	159.947583	2054.706961	...	...
4	1	48	18925.23	14.913540	15	2	0	17.087227	119.956640	2164.579412	...	...
5	0	83	40074.19	8.147417	16	2	1	1.670972	149.948316	271.493436	...	...

```
5 rows x 33 columns
```

```
# List features for analysis
features = (list(churn_df.columns[:-1]))
print('Features for analysis include: \n', features)

Features for analysis include:
['Children', 'Age', 'Income', 'Outage_sec_perweek', 'Email', 'Contacts', 'Yearly_equip_failure', 'Tenure', 'MonthlyCharge', 'Bandwidth_GB_Year', 'Timely_Response',
'Timely_Fixes', 'Timely_Replacements', 'Reliability', 'Options', 'Respectful_Response', 'Courteous_exchange', 'Active_Listening', 'DummyGender', 'DummyTechie', 'DummyContract',
'DummyPort_modem', 'DummyTablet', 'DummyInternetService', 'DummyPhone', 'DummyMultiple', 'DummyOnlineSecurity', 'DummyOnlineBackup', 'DummyDeviceProtection',
'DummyTechSupport', 'DummyStreamingTV', 'DummyPaperlessBilling']
```

CONCLUSION

This study explored the potential of K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) for predicting customer churn in a telecommunications company. After cleaning and preparing the data, a KNN model was trained and evaluated. The final model achieved an accuracy of 0.79 and a precision of 0.84, indicating a good ability to distinguish between churning and loyal customers. Additionally, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) score of 0.7959 further reinforces the model's effectiveness. However, it's important to acknowledge limitations. The choice of the K parameter in KNN significantly impacts the model's performance. Our initial choice of K=7 might not be optimal, and further exploration through techniques like cross-validation grid search could reveal a better value for K. Additionally, KNN can be computationally expensive, requiring significant processing power for large datasets. Despite these limitations, the KNN model offers valuable insights for customer retention strategies. Marketers and decision-makers should recognize that the accuracy of our predictions, while good, still leaves room for improvement. Analyzing churned customer profiles can reveal common characteristics that could be targeted with retention campaigns. The study suggests that offering bundled services and discounts to customers who subscribe to multiple services might incentivize them to stay. Ultimately, the goal is to enhance customer experience and satisfaction, leading to higher loyalty and reduced churn.

REFERENCES

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